

A Survey of Requirements for Thailand's Industry 4.0: The Perspectives from Academics and Entrepreneurs

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Abstract

The main objective of this study is to explore various requirements for improving skills and knowledges needed for Thailand's 4.0 industry. The findings are used to develop the Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0). The aim of this created program-based needs of instructors and employers is to serve high skilled and graduated students for commercial entrepreneurs. Likewise, academics can improve their teaching and learning approaches via the curriculum. In this study, the respondents are instructors and employers, who have working experience ranged from 0 to 10 years and greater. There are 225 participants from Bangkok and its suburbs, North, South, Northeast and West of Thailand agree to participate in the study. The respondents are allowed to assess their needs based on 16 required skills and knowledges: enterprise management in digital economy, project management for industry 4.0, smart operations management, quality management for extended enterprise, sustainable supply chain management, digital factory, advanced optimization, intelligent decision support systems, applied data analytics, cyber-physical industrial systems, collaborative manufacturing systems, additive manufacturing for industry 4.0, innovative product design and development, human-centric design for operator 4.0, customer experience-driven design, and leadership communication and people development in digital era. The results can promote the short training courses, which can be used to enhance the knowledge of instructors, graduates, and employers accurately. Moreover, the course learning outcomes (CLOs) of each subject in MSIE4.0 are focused and designed based on the guidelines of this study.

Keywords: Curriculum Requirements; Student Learning Outcomes; Required Skills; Industry 4.0.

1 Introduction

The rise of new digital industrial technology known as Industry 4.0 is a transformation that makes it possible to gather and analyze data across machines, enabling faster, more flexible, and more efficient processes to produce higher-quality goods at reduced costs (Oztemel & Gursev, 2020). This revolution improves the flexibility, speed, productivity, and quality of the production process including the foundation for the adoption of new business models (Li et al., 2017). Hence, manufacturers are facing a significant reskilling effort to capitalize on new opportunities while maintaining legacy automation environments. Those changes are powered by emerging technologies, offering a better way to organize and manage all standard processes within the manufacturing industry. The major problem of Industry 4.0 in Thailand is lacking of workers together with the rise of technologies of smart manufacturing (Koohathongsumrit & Luangpaiboon, 2020). This problem is preventing manufacturers from capitalizing on these trends due to as a result of lacking a properly skilled workforce (Hariharasudan & Kot, 2018). It is essential to promote vocational education and skill development in the country. The significant efforts are continuously increasing on skill development for Industry 4.0.

The Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0) project funded by the European Commission aims to develop a magister scientiae degree (MSc) for industrial engineering (IE) aligned with needs of Industry 4.0. The outcomes of this project are based on cooperation between 6 Thai and 3 European Union universities that after identifying the gap between the currently running programs and the needs of industry and students have prepared modernized studying program. Some activities of MSIE 4.0 are depicted in Figure 1. The curriculum is developed to propose students' learning outcomes covered Industry 4.0 technologies, management, and design approaches by the backward planning because of focusing the learning experiences rather than the teaching and learning methods including expertise (Kengpol, Koohathongsumrit, & Meethom, 2020; McElhinny, Dougherty, Bowling,

& Libarkin, 2014). Hence, graduated students are ready to work in Industry 4.0 and contribute to its sustainability based on the overarching curriculum. One of the components is needs of stakeholders, which can be used to identify a course in the curriculum. The course refers to many types of contents e.g. program learning outcomes (PLOs), course objectives, course learning outcomes (CLOs), dispositions, durations, course syllabus, learners, instructors, activities, resources, teaching guidelines, skills to be acquired, lexis, language structure, and assessment methods (Mingsakul, Usadornsak, Tuntitippawan, & Kengpol, 2020; Skerrett, 2010). Moreover, the course can be viewed as a measurable, observable, and specific statement that clearly indicates what a student should know and be able to do as a result of learning (Fogleman, McNeill, & Krajcik, 2011).

Figure 1. Some activities of MSIE 4.0.

For MSIE 4.0, The process of defining courses starts with the draft of PLOs and the challenge for consortium members on achieving them with IE courses. The draft list of courses has been the outcome of brain storming session of consortium members available on the meeting. The courses have gone through similar process as the list of PLOs. The consortium members have come to the short list of the courses with scoping, joining and re-orienting the courses submitted at the beginning. The list of courses is defined and illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. List of MSIE 4.0 courses.

No.	Course name	Course status
1	Enterprise Management in Digital Economy (EMDE)	elective
2	Project Management for Industry 4.0 (PMI)	elective
3	Smart Operations Management (SOM)	core
4	Quality Management for Extended Enterprise (QMEE)	elective
5	Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM)	elective
6	Digital Factory (DF)	core
7	Advanced Optimization: Techniques and Industrial Applications (AO)	elective
8	Intelligent Decision Support Systems (IDSS)	elective
9	Applied Data Analytics (ADA)	core
10	Cyber-Physical Industrial Systems (CPIS)	elective
11	Collaborative Manufacturing Systems (CMS)	elective
12	Additive Manufacturing for Industry 4.0 (AMI)	elective
13	Innovative Product Design and Development (IPDD)	elective
14	Human-Centric Design for Operator 4.0 (HCDO)	compulsory
15	Customer Experience-Driven Design (CEDD)	elective
16	Communications and People Skills Development for Engineering Leaders (CPSD)	elective

The aim of this study is to explore the required skills and knowledges for the smart technology in Thailand's industry 4.0 from academics and industrial entrepreneurs. The benefits of this study provide a guideline to develop the master's degree program for industrial sectors as well as the foundation for the quality of study and the success of a degree program.

2 Materials and Methods

This study is a survey research, which is the collection of the required skills and knowledges in Industry 4.0 attained by asking individuals questions either in person, on paper, by phone or online (Ruel, Wagner III, & Gillespie, 2016). The methods of this study aid instructors to gather data from its source that can be used to develop the new curriculum. The academics and industrial entrepreneurs are allowed to express their perspectives for the needs of skill in such situation. There are four steps to complete the gap of research, as described below (Delobelle et al., 2010; Rowley, 2014).

2.1 Participant Selection

Participant selection is the process of selecting a representative group from the population under study (Kramer et al., 2014). The Population of this study is academics and industrial entrepreneurs in Thailand. The academic is a full-time instructor in different universities apart from MSIE 4.0's partners. Regarding the industrial entrepreneurs can be defined as chief executive of industrial manufacturing company in Thailand. The invitations are individually sent to the interested population via email. If the respondents accept the invitations, they are determined as the participants. Therefore, a sample of this study is the respondents of target groups, who accept the invitations.

2.2 Questionnaire Design

The tool of this study is a questionnaire, which refers to a research instrument consisting of a list of standardized questions to gather useful information on the required skills and knowledges in Industry 4.0 from one or more participants (Mardani et al., 2016; Meethom & Koothongsumrit, 2018). The questions are answered by the participants in order to provide information for a report or a survey (de Boer, Timmerman, Pijl, & Minnaert, 2012). The online questionnaire is created based on five sections: (1) organization/university, (2) industrial type, (3) working area, (4) working experience, and (5) the required skills and knowledges. More details on the questionnaire can be found via this URL: <https://forms.gle/TeCvY4xh9zPCDBU9>. In the questionnaire, questions are designed to elicit information regarding the aforementioned measures. The number of questions in section 1 to 4 are equal to 4 whereas the questions in section 5 are equal to 16. The participants are allowed to choose the best answer in sections 1, 3 and 4 while section 2 and 5 permit the participant choose more than one answer. For the first section, the participants can select their characteristics: academic, industrial, and others fields. The second section presents the types of organizations: IE (T1), seafood processing (T2), logistics and transport (T3), packaging and commerce (T4), electronics (T5), automotive (T6), tourism (T7), agricultural processing (T8), construction and manufacturing (T9), aerospace (T10), petrochemical (T11), automation (T12), wood/furniture (T13), information technology (T14), textile industry (T15), manufacturing (T16), packaging (T17), and others (T18). The working areas in the third section are divided into Bangkok and its suburbs, North, South, Northeast and West. In the fourth section, the working experiences (years) can be classified into seven groups: less than or equal to 1 year (0-1), greater than 1 year but less than or equal to 3 years (2-3), greater than 3 years but less than or equal to 5 years (4-5), greater than 5 years but less than or equal to 7 years (6-7), greater than 7 year but less than or equal to 9 years (8-9), equal to 10 years, and greater than 10 years (>10). This study, the last section is the required skills and knowledges in Industry 4.0, the names of 16 courses are determined as the questions, which demonstrate the needs of skills and knowledges for Industry 4.0. In addition, the participants can check the course objectives by ticking on its names. The details of each course are shown in Table 2. However, the limitation of this questionnaire is that the requirements are assumed an equal importance. The participants can send an email for the intensity of importance to the MSIE 4.0's members.

Table 2. Objectives of 16 MSIE 4.0's courses.

Course	Objective
EMDE	This course aims to provide the students with knowledge and competences on using integrated and system solutions in advancing the management to the requirements of Digital Economy. In this course students will learn on how to adopt management, its strategies and functions to smart and sustainable solutions that 4.0 era has brought to enterprises. Students will learn how to use ICT management tools and solutions to enhance transformation from traditional to digital business operation and models.
PMI	This course concentrates to prepare graduates to perform in and manage projects and teams in the new highly agile digitized challenging smart industries. These projects will be developed by interdisciplinary distributed teams using digital platforms. The guidelines for dealing with a project service for each customer each time are presented as an increase in customized services that ultimately can become a service for each customer.
SOM	The course focuses to develop competences on design and implementation of continuous and efficient operations while creating a digital copy of the end-to-end process. Using real world data to understand, evaluate, and simulate the end-to-end operation to improve and manage all operations efficiently. Emphasis is on cross-enterprise integration of the physical and virtual systems among various functions including operation strategy, process design and planning, facility location and design, forecasting, scheduling and inventory control.
QMEE	This course aims to develop technical skill for students to implement quality control and monitoring system that cover both process operation and supply chain operations. A complete paragraph including a brief introduction connecting the course to sustainable smart industry, and what instructors would like to cover in the course
SSCM	This course aims to acquire the ability to create an effective value chain with the use of intelligent and flexible production technologies and modern communication as part of the interaction network between its participants. This course enables students to gain/improve knowledge of supply chain management that covers key issues regarding supply network design, inventory control and management, delivery contract, bullwhip and information exchange, distribution strategy, strategic alliance, purchasing strategies, pricing strategies, etc.
DF	This course presents utilization of digital technology for modeling, and communications to configure, model, simulate, assess, and operate a manufacturing process. A new set of rules for smart factory, including increased agility, new technology solutions, transparent communication, standardized planning processes, a shortened product development, and cross-functional teams is provided.
AO	The objective of this course is to provide the students knowledge on the application of various optimization techniques which can help making decisions for practical problems in industries. Modeling concepts and applications of linear, integer, nonlinear, and dynamic programming as well as network models are addressed. Meta-heuristic techniques are also discussed to obtain solutions for large scale practical problems.
IDSS	The target of this course is to give students the up-to-date of decision-making concepts, process, strategies, and technologies that are often used to support decision making in real-world issues coupled with agile approach and industry 4.0 specification, and design decision support system by mini project. A decision support system with embedded artificial intelligence techniques exhibiting some or all of the abilities indicative of intelligent behavior is proposed.
ADA	This course aims to impart knowledge on statistical techniques needed for data analysis, and various data mining techniques and algorithms used in practical problems that require processing big data for decision making purpose. Moreover, many techniques and processes of data analytics automated into mechanical processes and algorithms that work over raw data for human consumption are clarified.
CPIS	The main characteristics of this course to express systems of collaborating computational entities which are in intensive connection with the surrounding physical world and its on-going processes, providing and using, at the same time, data-accessing and data-processing services available on the internet. The applicaion, components, selection rules, programming methodology, specific aspects related to different measured physical parameters, data storage, reporting and communications are included.
CMS	The course is creating knowledge and is developing technical competence for better understanding of future emerging sustainable smart manufacturing systems. This course is also presenting and analyzing modern methods and techniques, which will compete on design and operation of agile, lean, green, and sustainable manufacturing systems. Teaching technique is centered on project based learning type activities allowing flexible learning formats.

Table 2. Cont.

Course	Objective
AMI	This course aims to describe the sustainable rapid development of personalized complex design in various disruptive applications, especially in manufacturing and medical. The students are trained to gain the competence in additive manufacturing and related technology. The students will learn fundamental knowledge of additive manufacturing and reverse engineering and their applications of in manufacturing, medical and other sectors. Besides, they will learn and practice design for additive manufacturing.
IPDD	The subject of the course concerns the creative design of innovative products that are technological innovation or modification of existing technological solutions. As a result, designed products should find their application in Industry 4.0 related businesses and its problems. The goal of this course is discussion of issues related to development and marketing innovative products, including searching for ideas and creating a concept based on creative thinking techniques and methods of entrepreneurial problem solving, selecting ideas and development of prototypes, taking into account user needs and the latest scientific research.
HCDO	Human-centric design is a unique approach to solve problems of products, process, environments, and other human operations challenging with incompatibilities of human needs, abilities and limitations. The objective of this course is to evaluate and design tasks, equipment, products, processes, jobs, environments and other elements in working systems in order to optimize human wellbeing and overall system performance.
CEDD	This course aims to build student competence in design customer experience with knowledge on a concept of customer experience management (CEM) and on a systematic approach for an experience design process. In this course, the students will learn customer perception, customer involvement, and customer experience. Besides, they will learn and practice how to design customer journey and to prevent failure of offering in a team environment.
CPSD	This course aims to develop the best of each person in the context of their professional practice, will create a competitive advantage. Additionally, the communication between different cultures and for different types of audiences will make the best of leaders. This course aims to prepare graduates for leadership in companies, communicating effectively and developing people to their best.

2.3 Data Collection

The questionnaires are separately distributed to the participants between October 2019 and March 2020. The link of questionnaire is then sent to the participants via email. In some cases, the hard copies of questionnaires are also distributed to the participants, who give their affiliations in recommendation form of invitation. The respondents have to answer the questions on their own. For the fifth sections, the participants can give their data more than one answer.

3 Results and Discussion

This section describes the number of participants and the findings. The general information of participants as organization/university, industrial type, working area, and working experience are characterized. With regard to the required skills and knowledges, they are analyzed by the ratio and proportion. There are 225 participants, who accept the invitations. They contain 207 participants from industrial sectors and 18 instructors from the universities in Thailand. The participants are classified based work areas. Table 3 shows that there are 10 academics and 97 entrepreneurs from Bangkok and its suburbs, 3 academics and 43 entrepreneurs from North, 2 academics and 21 entrepreneurs from South, 4 academics and 32 entrepreneurs from Northeast, and 14 entrepreneurs from West. The academics from West do not response to participate in this study.

Furthermore, the participants can be divided into 17 groups based on the types of organizations, Table 4 illustrates that there are 18 participants from T1, 6 participants from T2, 35 participants from T3, 20 participants from T4, 17 participants from T5, 27 participants from T6, 3 participants from T7, 9 participants from T8, 12 participants from T9, 2 participants from T10, 1 participants from T11, 7 participants from T12, 5 participants from T13, 11 participants from T14, 8 participants from T15, 31 participants from T16, and 13 participants from T17. However, participants from other types of organizations do not cooperate in this study.

Table 3. Participants in this study.

Sector	Work Area					Total
	Bangkok/ its suburbs	North	South	Northeast	West	
Academics	10	3	2	3	0	18
Industrial Entrepreneurs	97	43	21	32	14	207
Total	107	46	23	35	14	225

Table 4. Participants grouped by types of organization.

	Types of Organization																		Total
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T9	T10	T11	T12	T13	T14	T15	T16	T17	T18	
Participant	18	6	35	20	17	27	3	9	12	2	1	7	5	11	8	31	13	0	225

According to the working experience, the participants consist of 7 different groups, as mentioned in Section 2.2. The first group has 52 participants; the second group has 55 participants; the third group has 45 participants; the fourth group has 36 participants; the fifth group has 21 participants; the sixth group has 12 participants; and the last group has 4 participants, as given in Table 5. The results show that the number of participants grouped by working experiences and the response rate have a negative correlation.

Table 5. Participants grouped by working experiences.

	Working Experiences (Years)							Total
	0-1	2-3	4-5	6-7	8-9	10	>10	
Participant	52	55	45	36	21	12	4	225

For the fifth section, the participants answer and check the skills and knowledges, which are presented as the MSIE 4.0's courses. They can give their scores more than one choice. If the participant checks the course, it means the skills and knowledges in such course is essential to work in Industry 4.0. The participants' answers are transformed and interpreted by the percentage of observations, as shown in Table 6. Nonetheless, the maximum needs of skills and knowledges corresponding to each course are equal to 225.

Table 6. Participants' answers of skills and knowledges needed in Industry 4.0.

	Course															
	EMDE	PMI	SOM	QMEE	SSCM	DF	AO	IDSS	ADA	CPIS	CMS	AMI	IPDD	HCDO	CEDD	CPSD
Academics	3	2	4	4	<u>13</u>	<u>12</u>	5	6	<u>7</u>	4	4	6	5	4	4	4
(Percentage)	(16.61)	(11.11)	(22.22)	(22.22)	<u>(72.22)</u>	<u>(66.67)</u>	(27.78)	(33.33)	<u>(38.89)</u>	(22.22)	(22.22)	(33.33)	(27.78)	(22.22)	(22.22)	(22.22)
Industrial Entrepreneurs	47	48	77	55	<u>154</u>	<u>158</u>	59	79	<u>160</u>	67	111	47	103	57	62	73
(Percentage)	(22.71)	(23.19)	(37.20)	(26.57)	<u>(74.40)</u>	<u>(76.33)</u>	(28.50)	(38.16)	<u>(77.29)</u>	(32.37)	(53.62)	(22.71)	(49.76)	(27.54)	(29.95)	(35.27)
Total	50	50	81	59	<u>167</u>	<u>170</u>	64	85	<u>167</u>	71	<u>115</u>	53	108	61	66	77
(Percentage)	(22.22)	(22.22)	(36.00)	(26.22)	<u>(74.22)</u>	<u>(75.60)</u>	(28.44)	(37.78)	<u>(74.22)</u>	(31.56)	<u>(51.11)</u>	(23.56)	(48.00)	(27.11)	(29.33)	(34.22)

Based on Table 6, the skills and knowledges needed based on academics' perspectives can be rank in descending order as SSCM > DF > ADA > IPDD, IDSS > IPDD, AO > SOM, QMEE, CPIS, CMS, HCDO, CEDD, CPSD > EDMDE > PMI. The SSCM is taken the most necessary course due to the highest percentage of required skills and knowledges as 72.22 percent. DF and ADA take the second and third most necessary course. For the industrial entrepreneurs' perspectives, they need the ADA because of the highest percentage. The industrial entrepreneurs' ranking is ADA > DF > SSCM > CMS > IPDD > IDSS > SOM > CPSD > CPIS > CEDD > AO > HCDO > QMEE > PMI > EMDE, AMI. With regard to the total participants, the top four courses are DF at 75.60 percent, SSCM and ADA at 74.22 percent for each course, and CMS at 51.11 percent. The remaining courses are IPDD at 48.00 percent, IDSS at 37.78 percent, SOM at 36.00 percent, CPSD at 34.22 percent, CPIS at 31.56 percent, CEDD at 29.33 percent, AO at 28.44 percent, HCDO at 27.11 percent, QMEE at 26.22 percent, AMI at 23.56 percent, and EMDE including PMI at 22.22 percent. The participants' answers of skills and knowledges needed in Industry 4.0 are depicted in Figure 2. Furthermore, the results demonstrate that the most important required skills and knowledges needed in Thailand's Industry 4.0 is DF with 75.6 percent, followed by SSCM and ADA with 74.22 percent for each course, and CMS with 51.11 percent. These courses are the application of digital technologies that create opportunities for differentiation in the marketplace, for enhancing the efficiency of the production system and improving on-time performances.

Figure 2. Participants' answers of skills and knowledges needed in Industry 4.0.

The findings show that the perspectives of academics and entrepreneurs are not different. The essential skills for industry 4.0 can be categorized into six skills: technology, programming, digital, thinking, society, and personality skills. The hard skills for industry 4.0 include the processes of inspecting, cleansing, transforming, and modeling data with the goal of discovering useful information for supply chain, data processing, smart manufacturing, and digital technology in plants. The soft skills are an interaction between manpower and machine. All kinds of skills for using of artificial intelligence are necessary concentrated to promote the controlling and monitoring a digital machinery in order to increase productivity. However, an education in Thailand has changed dramatically due to the outbreak of coronavirus diseases (COVID-19). As a result, the 16 courses are undertaken remotely and on digital platforms. Whereby, semesters after the ending of the outbreak, the online and traditional learnings are simultaneously proceeded.

4 Conclusions

The objective of this study is to investigate the needs of skills and knowledges for designing the master curriculum for IE. The skills and knowledges of MSIE 4.0 are classified into 16 different courses: SSCM, DF, AO, IDSS, ADA, CPIS, CMS, AMI, IPDD, HCDO, CEDD, and CPSD. The participants of this study are academics of IE and industrial entrepreneurs, who work in Thailand. The questionnaire is designed and individually distributed to the 225 participants. The results show that the most significant required skills and knowledges needed in Thailand's Industry 4.0 based on the perspectives of academics and industrial entrepreneurs are SSCM, DF, ADA, and CMS followed by the remaining courses in descending order as IPDD, IDSS, SOM, CPSD, CPIS, CEDD, AO, HCDO, QMEE, AMI, and EMDE as well as PMI. The contributions of this study provide guidelines for in-

demand skills and knowledges needed in Thailand's Industry 4.0 as well as more coherent learning paths. For the future study, a CLO for every course is developed to identify contributions of each course in the master curriculum of science in IE. The requirements can be collected by the proposed guideline-based the Delphi method developed by Meethom and Koohathongsumrit (2020)

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